

Insect antifeedant potent chalcones

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Abstract : Some halogen substituted 2-propen-1-ones were synthesized by solvent free eco-friendly method. They are characterized by physical constants, analytical and spectral data. Their antifeedant activity against castor *semilooper* and *Achoea janata* L. has been studied. The chlorinated chalcones were found to be most effective.

Keywords : Chalcones, eco-friendly synthesis, grind stone chemistry, insect antifeedant activity.

Introduction

In recent years organic chemist and scientists¹ have paid much more interest to solvent free industrial non-hazardous synthetic methods to synthesize organic substrates through various chemical reactions² due to synthetic operative simplicity, easier work up, better yield, non-toxic and environmentally eco-friendly nature. Many reagents and coordination complexes have been employed for solvent free aldol condensation³⁻⁹. The author wish to report an efficient and selective method for condensation of aryl ketones with various *m*- and *p*-substituted

benzaldehydes under solvent free conditions by grinding the reactants with potassium hydroxide in a mortar to yields the respective *E*-2-propen-1-ones. In this method during grinding of biphenyl, fluorene and naphthyl ketones are slowly decomposed forming the products in good yield and the reaction time is lesser than that in solution.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All chemicals and AnalaR grade solvents were pur-

Table 1. Physical constants and analytical data of 4-methyl-1-naphthyl-2-propen-1-ones

Entry	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Found (Calcd.) (%)		Mass fragmentation
				C	H	
(2 <i>E</i>)-3-(3-Bromophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one						
6a	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrO	126-127	74	68.30 (68.39)	4.25 (4.30)	352 (97%), 351 (22%), 350 (100%) [M ⁺], 337 (63%), 335 (87%), 271 (45%), 212 (23%), 210 (47%), 208 (32%), 182 (42%), 195 (65%), 169 (18%), 156 (13%), 155 (63%), 141 (27%), 77 (67%), 15 (42%)
(2 <i>E</i>)-3-(3-Chlorophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one						
6b	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClO	97-98	68	78.25 (78.30)	4.86 (4.93)	308 (32%), 307 (25%), 306 (100%) [M ⁺], 293 (41%), 291 (45%), 169 (59%), 171 (33%), 143 (15%), 141 (40%), 129 (17%), 127 (33%), 77 (65%), 55 (51%), 15 (25%)
(2 <i>E</i>)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one						
6c	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClO	80-81	72	78.28 (78.30)	4.90 (4.93)	308 (33%), 307 (22%), 306 (100%) [M ⁺], 293 (39%), 291 (43%), 273 (58%), 271 (63%), 195 (38%), 169 (53%), 167 (41%), 165 (63%), 141 (23%), 139 (31%), 127 (56%), 113 (25%), 77 (68%), 55 (70%), 15 (53%)

chased from E. Merck chemical company. Melting points were determined in open glass capillaries on Mettler FP51 melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Fourier transform spectrophotometer in KBr ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) discs. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on INSTRUM DPX-200 model 300 MHz spectrometer operating at 300 MHz frequency for recording ^1H NMR spectra and 75.45 MHz frequency for recording ^{13}C NMR spectra, TMS as internal standard. Electron impact (EI) (70 eV) and chemical ionization (CI) were recorded with a Finnigan MAT 95S spectrometer. The micro analyses of the chalcones were performed in Perkin-Elmer 240C Analyzer and obtained is presented in Table 1.

General procedure for synthesis of 2-propen-1-ones :

Appropriate mixture of biphenyl, 9H-fluorene and 4-substituted 1-naphthyl ketones (0.01 mol) and *m*- and *p*-substituted benzaldehydes (0.01 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.02 mol) in a mortar was ground with pestle (Scheme 1). After completion of reaction was confirmed by TLC, the reaction mixture was transferred into cold water in a 25 ml corning glass beaker and filtered. The product yield is more than 65%, was filtered, dried and recrystallised with ethanol-dioxane mixture and again dried in vacuum desiccator. The known compound characters are compared with authentic samples and physical constants and spectral data. The spectral data of selective compounds are summarized (6a-c).

6a. (2*E*)-3-(3-Bromophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one : IR (KBr, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 1654 (CO *s-cis*), 1636 (CO *s-trans*), 1033 (CH=CH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 8.102 (1H, d, H- α), 8.161 (1H, d, H- β), 7.342–7.892 (10H, m, Ar-H), 2.695 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 191.700 (CO), 122.40 (C- α), 140.818 (C- β), 22.803 (CH_3).

6b. (2*E*)-3-(3-Chlorophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one : IR (KBr, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 1657 (CO *s-cis*), 1629 (CO *s-trans*), 1029 (CH=CH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 8.315 (1H, d, H- α), 8.327 (1H, d, H- β), 7.320–7.843 (10H, m, Ar-H), 2.864 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 192.784 (CO), 123.662 (C- α), 141.886 (C- β), 23.782 (CH_3).

6c. (2*E*)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1-(4-methyl-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one : IR (KBr, $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 1655 (CO *s-cis*), 1631 (CO *s-trans*), 1013 (CH=CH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 8.174 (1H, d, H- α), 8.297 (1H, d, H- β), 7.129–8.000 (10H, m, Ar-H), 2.395 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 193.617 (CO), 122.966 (C- α), 142.997 (C- β), 23.612 (CH_3).

Entry	R	X	Ref.
1a	4-Biphenyl	<i>m</i> -Br	10
1b	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	11
1c	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	11
2a	9H-2-Fluorenyl	<i>m</i> -Br	10
2b	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	11
2c	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	11
3a	4-Bromo-1-naphthyl	H	1a
3b	"	<i>m</i> -NH ₂	1a
3c	"	<i>p</i> -NH ₂	1a
3d	"	<i>m</i> -Br	1a
3e	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	1a
3f	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	1a
3g	"	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	1a
3h	"	<i>p</i> -OH	1a
3i	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	1a
3j	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	1a
3k	"	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	1a
3l	"	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1a
3m	"	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1a
4a	4-Chloro-1-naphthyl	H	12
4b	"	<i>m</i> -NH ₂	12
4c	"	<i>p</i> -NH ₂	12
4d	"	<i>m</i> -Br	12
4e	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	12
4f	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	12
4g	"	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	12
4h	"	<i>p</i> -OH	12
4i	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	12
4j	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	12
4k	"	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	12
4l	"	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	12
4m	"	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	12
5a	4-Methoxy-1-naphthyl	<i>m</i> -Br	13
5b	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	13
5c	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	13
6a	4-Methyl-1-naphthyl	<i>m</i> -Br	—
6b	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	—
6c	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	—

Scheme 1

Table 3. Antifeedant activity of compound **4e** (2*E*)-1-(4-chloro-1-naphthyl)-3-(3-chlorophenyl)-2-propen-1-one at 4 different concentrations

ppm ↓	Number of leaf discs consumed by the insect (values are mean + SE of five)									Total leaf disc consumed in 24 h
	4-6 pm 2 h	6-8 pm 4 h	8-10 pm 6 h	10-12 pm 8 h	12pm- 6am 14 h	6-8 am 16 h	8am- 12Nn 20 h	12Nn- 2pm 22 h	2-4 pm 24 h	
50	0.5	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.5
100	0	0.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.25
150	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Insect antifeedant activity :

Chalcones possess a wide range of biological activities¹⁴ such as antifungal, antibacterial, antiviral and antifeedant activity. These multipronged activities present in different chalcones are intended to examine their insect antifeedant activities against caterpillar *semilooper*. The larvae of *Achoea janata* L. were reared as described on the leaves of caterpillar *Ricinus communis* in the laboratory at the temperature range of 26 ± 1 °C and a relative humidity of 75–85%. The leaf-disc bioassay method¹⁵ was used against the 4th instar larvae to measure the antifeedant activity. The 4th instar larvae were selected for testing because the larvae at this stage feed very voraciously.

Measurement of insect antifeedant activity of chalcones :

Leaf discs of a diameter of 1.85 cm were punched from caterpillar leaves with the petioles intact. All ketones were dissolved in acetone at a concentration of 200 ppm dipped for 5 min. The leaf discs were air-dried and placed in one liter beaker containing little water in order to facilitate translocation of water. Therefore the leaf disc remains fresh throughout the duration of the test, 4th instar larvae of the test insect, which had been preserved on the leaf discs of all chalcones and allowed to feed on them for 24 h. The area of the leaf disc consumed was measured by Dethlers¹⁶ method. The observed antifeedant activity of chalcones was presented in Table 2.

The results of the antifeedant activity of 2-propen-1-ones presented in Table 2 reveals that the compound **4d** is found to reflect remarkable antifeedant among all other chalcones. This test is performed with the insects which are only two-leaf disc soaked under the solution of this compound. Compound **4d** also show enough antifeedant activity but lesser than **4e**. Further compound **4e** was subjected to measure the antifeedant activity at different 50, 100, 150 ppm concentrations and the observation reveals that as the concentrations decreased, the activity also decreased. It is observed from the results in Table 3 that the ketones. Chalcone **4e** (2*E*)-1-(4-chloro-1-naph-

thyl)-3-(3-chlorophenyl)-2-propen-1-one shows an appreciable antifeedant activity at 200 ppm concentration.

Conclusions :

A simple non-hazardous eco-friendly method for the synthesis of biphenyl and 9*H*-fluorenyl chalcones using solvent free condition has been developed by grinding the reactants. The advantages of this method include mild reaction condition, reduced the reaction time, good yield, slow decomposition to formation of products. About their antifeedant activities, compound **4e** shows appreciable antifeedant activity at 200 ppm concentration.

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